

Identification of levers and barriers for the adoption of new ATM technologies¹

Delhaye, E. (Transport & Mobility Leuven & KU Leuven); Van der loo S.; Heyndrickx, C. (Transport & Mobility Leuven)

Zheng Zhang, D., Fabio, A. (CRIDA)

Abstract

This work analyses the main levers and barriers for the adoption of innovative technologies within Air Traffic Management (ATM). The main goal is to find promising policy and regulatory measures. These should increase the speed of uptake of innovative technologies while at the same time take into account elements such as acceptability, feasibility, and efficiency.

Qualitative and quantitative methods are employed. The qualitative assessment is based on literature review, interviews with ATM stakeholders and a workshop. The goal is to

- identify explanatory factors behind the experiences, helping us understand the reasons and conditions for success/failure of the implementation of technologies.
- depict mechanisms and promising policy measures linked to the adoption of technologies,

which are then further investigated using an economic model and a multicriteria analysis (quantitative assessment).

We find that reducing the gap between research and deployment phases by increasing technology maturity level; a better dissemination strategy; and the involvement of different stakeholders (including Safety Agencies) in both research and deployment phases would fasten the adoption. Increasing human and financial resources; and a change in the business model advances the acceptability of innovative technologies.

From the quantitative analysis, the first insight is that regulation of navigation fees should be as flexible as possible. The second insight is that the market uptake of technologies in a one-to-one setting is easier. The third insight is that it is not clear if increased competition between ANSPs will stimulate the uptake of technologies. The fourth insight is that a mandate for a 'proven' technology can be welfare improving.

The conclusions of both the initial qualitative assessment and the economic modelling are then used within a multicriteria analysis to define a set of promising policy and regulatory measures.

¹ This project has received funding from the SJU under grant agreement No 893443 under European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program

1. Introduction

Innovation is a complex phenomenon. It depends not only on the development of innovative technologies, but also on the **existence of regulation and institutions able to facilitate and foster the implementation** of such technologies. A sound understanding of the economical, behavioural, and societal factors that influence the uptake of innovative technologies in Air Traffic Management (ATM) is essential for shaping effective policies and regulations that aim a successful implementation of innovations.

The **SESAR ITACA project** investigates the technology uptake pace in the ATM system and aims to **support policy making decisions aimed at accelerating the development, adoption, and deployment of innovative technologies in ATM**. To achieve this general objective, **ITACA develops a new set of methodologies and tools** enabling the rigorous and comprehensive **assessment of policies and regulations** aimed at amplifying the uptake of innovative technologies within ATM. We use a combination of methodologies: qualitative assessment, economic modelling, agent based modelling and serious games.

The work presented here forms the starting point of the ITACA project. We assess qualitatively the main barriers and levers, how these can be linked to policy measures, and what is the acceptability and applicability of these measures. This is, firstly, based on a review of literature and case studies of successful and unsuccessful experiences with the uptake of innovative technologies, interviews, and an online workshop. In the second part, we take a more quantitative approach with a theoretical analysis, which is illustrated with two numerical examples. The analysis uses elements of principal-agent modelling game theory and transport economics.

2. Qualitative assessment

Within this section we make a qualitative assessment of the main barriers and levers of technology uptake within ATM. First, we review literature and case studies of successful and unsuccessful experiences related to the uptake of new technologies. The primary focus of the case studies is on innovation in the aviation sector, but also includes the experience in other industries, especially in network industries such as rail, electricity, and telecommunications. Secondly, personal interviews and an online workshop with different stakeholders is used to identify the potential explanatory factors behind the reviewed experiences, helping us understand the reasons and conditions (e.g., level of competition, product lifetime cycles, etc.) for the success or failure of the implementation of new technologies.

2.1. Literature review

Economic research focusing on ATM is not abundant. Even less research has investigated the drivers behind the uptake of ATM technologies and/or new concepts². Fields where the uptake of technology has been researched are sociology, industrial economics (Belleflamme, P. & M. Peitz, (2012),) and organisation and management sciences. This research consists of descriptive analyses discussing the uptake of different technologies in different industries, empirical assessments of technology uptake and diffusion (using econometrics), economic models (industrial economics and game-theory) and behavioural and simulation models (Agent-Based Modelling).

² We use “technology” in the remainder of the text, but this should be interpreted in the broadest sense. It could also stand for the uptake of a certain concept for which investments in technology may or may not be needed.

Research on technology uptake took off by the classic work of Schumpeter, J.A. (1943) and Arrow, K. (1962), which focused on the relationship between market structure and the incentives for Research and Development (R&D). Today, there is a consensus that this relationship has an inverted U-shape: perfect competition leaves no profit for innovation, while within a perfect monopoly there are no real incentives. This is particularly relevant for ATM, with ANSPs being **monopolistic by nature** and an aviation market working in a competitive environment. The seminal work of Rogers, E.M. (1962, 2010) not only discusses the incentives to innovate but also the diffusion of innovations within an industry/society. A growing body of information shows that human factors and organisational/environmental factors play a significant role in determining the success or failure of technology transfer and commercialisation ventures (Roupas, P., 2008). Research focussing on ATM has identified some potential causes of the slow technology uptake. Within the economic modelling of the WP-E ACCHANGE project, **fragmentation of the market, price regulation, home bias and the power of the unions** came out as crucial elements influencing the efficiency of Air Navigation Service Providers (ANSPs). The SESAR ER COMPAIR project focused on the issue of national monopolies and the introduction of some forms of competition as the solution to encourage ANSPs to invest in technologies.

The work of Papazoglou, M.E, Spanos, Y.E (2018) focuses on the factors influencing technology diffusion, with one of these factors being the technology itself and their characteristics. Within ATM many technologies are characterised by: (i) **network features**, in which the full benefits of upgrading a system are only realised if the whole network is upgraded leading to externalities and hence non-optimal investments; (ii) **“last mover advantage”**, in which stakeholders tend to postpone their investments knowing that benefits only arrive when all stakeholders are equipped with the new technology; and (iii) the need to take into account **the legacy technologies** used by other countries/partners, etc. [4] focuses on the role of the user consultation process in the decision-making by ANSPs. She states that this consultation process is hindered by: (i) the fact that the users are a diverse group (small and large airlines, national and international, cargo, general aviation, etc), (ii) the free rider problem (the benefits are for all the users, irrespective of who invested time and resources in the consultation process) and (iii) the complexity of the technologies. As causes of the slow uptake of technologies, she also adds the element of safety and the fact that operational disruptions in the system are not possible.

Hence, there is not a single reason for the slow uptake of technologies within ATM, but a combination of different, interactive factors. The next sections focus on some specific examples within ATM/aviation and in other industries to get a first flavour of which are the most important enablers and barriers.

2.1.1. Case studies Air Traffic Management

Three examples are discussed for ATM: **datalink**, the uptake of **space-based Automatic Dependent Surveillance-Broadcast (ADS-B)** and **remote towers**. Datalink refers to the digital air/ground communication between aircraft and ground systems. ADS-B is an air traffic surveillance technology that relies on aircraft broadcasting their identity, a precise Global Positioning System position and other information derived from on-board systems. It is automatic as no work is required from the pilot or the Air Traffic Controller (ATCO). Space-based means that information is transmitted using satellite-to-satellite communication. Both are interesting examples as they require that ANSPs, aircrafts (and airports) are equipped, the costs and benefits are different for the different stakeholders and the experience is different between different regions. Remote tower service is a system which allows aerodrome air traffic control of flight information service to be provided from a location other than the aerodrome whilst maintaining a level of operational safety which is equivalent to that achievable

using a staffed tower at the aerodrome³. It is an interesting example, the potential benefits are large and even larger if the provision at more than one aerodrome would happen from one single remote location- also called Remote Tower Centre. It is an example where the investment costs are (usually) for the airports, which together with the airlines also have benefits from the investment – especially when the remote tower can be shared, while ANSPs lose revenue.

The three “ATM technologies” all have in common that their implementation level differs across regions (European Union, United States and Canada). The table below summarizes the observed main drivers and barriers for the implementation of these three technologies. As the implementation of some of them is different in different regions it is possible that a certain policy is listed both as a barrier and a lever. For example, the efficiency of a mandate is correlated with the enforcement of the mandate.

Table 1: Levers and barriers ATM/Aviation technologies

Technology	Barriers	Levers
Data Link	High costs ANSPs/Budget constrains Principal-agent problem: main benefit for users – who do not bear the major share of the investment Stakeholders with different objectives Last mover advantage Safety concerns Reluctance to change Unrealistic timelines Fragmentation airspace Technical issues	Differentiated charges Promotion of technology Phased approach Realistic timelines Coordination efforts Mandate
ADS-B	Lack of enforcement Reluctance to change Fragmentation airspace Technology uncertainty Use of static and stringent standards Last mover advantage Costs for ANSPs	Mandates with strict enforcement Realistic timelines
Remote Tower Control	Opposition ATCOs Safety concerns Complexity	Large potential benefits Potential as contingency service Regional forerunners (starting at small airports)

2.1.2. Case studies other industries

To draw lessons for ATM the case studies focussed on experiences in other network industries such as rail, telecom and energy.

For rail we discuss the adoption of ERTMS, a common railway signalling system. Its implementation has, however, been much more expensive and slower than anticipated. ERTMS has been in development since the nineties. The aim was to replace the 20 different systems with one common system which had been jointly developed by eight companies. European Court of Auditors (2017) noted that between 2007-2020 about 4 billion euros were allocated towards ERTMS and that at the

³ https://www.skybrary.aero/index.php/Remote_Tower_Service

same time the development has been low and fragmented. This even if, in principle, the railway industry supported the idea, the timing was right (as several networks had to consider their control-command system especially due to the high-speed development) [48] and that already in 2002, the first technical specifications for ERTMS interoperability became legally binding.

For telecom we focussed on the technology of packet switching and its role within the internet revolution. The initial goal of the internet was to connect computers. This was first done over the telephone lines which was costly due to monopoly pricing and the use of circuit switching which was not very well suited for this. "Package switching" allowed for a better dynamic allocation as it gave much more freedom for traffic to move (transmission is no longer synchronised). This technology was already possible in the sixties, but telecom engineers were reluctant to change as there was no real need for it at the time. The real change came with a group of outsiders, computer professionals, which had a fundamental different starting point. They demonstrated in 1972 that this concept worked and was not a mere theoretical concept. By 1978 already, virtually all new data networks were based on packet-switching (GLass et al, 2018). This on its turn facilitated the break-up of the value chain and opened the door for more competition. The role of outsiders (IT, media, financial services) within technology uptake within the telecom industry is also emphasised by Berkhout, A.J & P.A. van der Duin (2007).

The energy case studies look at two related concepts: the take-up of battery electric vehicles (BEV) and the smart grid which allows a Vehicle-To-Grid (V2G) and a Grid-To-Vehicle (G2V) relationship. To reduce CO2 emissions, policy makers are looking at both the demand and the supply of energy. On the demand side much of the attention goes to battery electric vehicles (and heat pumps), on the supply side the focus goes to Renewable Energy Sources (RES) such as wind and waterpower but also to residential solar panels. Important is the potential synergy between them. An important disadvantage of RES is the volatility of the supply combined with the difficulty of storing energy. BEVs on the other hand could be seen as disconnected storage facility (G2V) where excess power could be stored, and even brought back to the network (V2G). However, in practice there are still many barriers to overcome. At the demand side, it is clear that, except for Norway with 75% of all new passenger car registrations a BEV or Plug in Hybrid Electric Vehicle (PHEV), the uptake of electric vehicles is still relatively low. Although the share of electric vehicles in the European fleet increased from 3.6% in 2019 to 11.0% in 2020 (European Alternative Fuels Observatory, 2021). (Berkeley et al, 2013) and (Greene et al, 2014) give an overview of the main drivers and barriers to the take-up of BEVs. They emphasise that one must look beyond the economic and technological dimensions to overcome the barriers and hence should also look at institutions, infrastructure, and society.

The next table shows the observed drivers and barriers from the technologies discussed in the other industries.

Table 2: Levers and barriers "other industries"

Technology	Barriers	Levers
ERTMS	Unstable specifications -> different systems -> compatibility issues Fragmentation network - network effect Lack of enforcement Reluctance to change Underestimation costs + gold-plating	Condition for receiving subsidies In some countries needed to be replaced anyway Regional forerunners (start with smaller networks) Stronger policy

	Large number of actors	
Telecom – packet switching	Reluctance to change Price regulation (cost pricing) Reliability Human capital Mixed ownership	Flexibility in regulation Competition with other providers Political pressure Liberalisation Financial market Separation technology – services Outsiders
Energy – BEV	Changing policy measures High costs Uncertainty on actual costs and benefits Risk aversion consumers Many actors involved Reluctance OEMs Technical limitations Lack of vehicle choice Shortage loading infrastructure Reluctance OEMs	Outsiders – niche markets (Tesla) Mandates Subsidies Adaptive policy
Energy – smart grid	Battery degradation Many BEV needed Reluctance electric suppliers Reluctance consumers Lobbying oil industry (Cyber) security Data protection issues Technological uncertainty	Real time pricing New players Multi-actor approach Integrated R&D pathway

Comparing the experiences in the other industries with the experiences in the aviation/ATM sectors we see that similar barriers arise. This is expected as we focussed on other industries which shared some of the main characteristics (national monopolies, network industries, large number of actors...) with ATM. Hence in most of these experiences the uptake of technology was slow. An important exception is the telecom industry which changed drastically over the last 30 years. From this experience, and most relevant for ATM, we learn the importance of

- The role of demonstration that something actual works (see data switching).
- The role of outsiders with a different viewpoint (computer specialists).
- The role of flexibility in (price) regulation – although unintentional at the start.
- The need for some competitive forces.

2.2. Stakeholder consultation

To identify the main barriers and levers with respect to the uptake of technologies within ATM; the importance of several factors during the decision process and the decision flow mechanisms within the organization of the stakeholders a set of interviews have been conducted with different stakeholders within the ATM world. Additionally, a workshop was organized to collect further

feedback on the identification of levers and barriers, to make the link between barriers and potential solutions and to receive some feedback on a first set of selected potential policy measures. The workshop took place with about 20 participants of different stakeholders' profiles.

In the following sub-sections, the results of both the interviews and the workshop are presented (consolidated).

2.2.1. Barriers and potential solutions

All interviewees agreed that the uptake of technologies within aviation was **slow to extremely slow**. Even up to the point that some technologies were obsolete by the time of implementation. This leads to some frustration as concepts with immense potential are lagging. Some argue that the uptake of technologies should be slow due to the safety considerations, but that in any case it should go faster than the current pace.

A long list of barriers was identified. Only the most important barriers with identified potential solutions are presented here:

1. Home bias in development and lack of standards

Home bias leading to a preference of inhouse development which on its turn hinders interoperability and the customer basis.

This barrier **might not be relevant for airports** due to two main reasons: (1) the small size of some airports leads to outsourcing given the available resources; and (2) the lack of expertise developing complex systems in house. **Airlines** usually avoid in-house developments. From the business case perspective, it is important to get higher levels of amortizations.

From the **Air Navigation Service Provider (ANSP) perspective**, in some cases, it might be quicker to implement a development if it is made in house. Depending on the nature of the technology to be developed, most ANSPs do not have either the capabilities to afford in-house developments (e.g., Virtual Centres) or the expertise in defining functional requirements (i.e., requirement language).

There is a lack of standards (operational or technical) for ANSPs and National Safety Authorities (NSAs) to be followed. They have their own standards, which make it diverse. Different standards of a same technology led to ambiguity and confusion (e.g., software standards).

Participants proposed the following **mitigation measures** to speed up the adoption of innovative technologies:

- **Avoid vertical integration:** clearly differentiate between the data provider, the service provider, and the user.
- **Transition to service-oriented architecture.**
- **Stronger performance regulation to create market conditions.**
- **Incentivize the adoption of innovative technologies, for example by rewarding early adopters.**

2. Complex system with many interdependencies

ATM is a complex system with a lot of stakeholders, many different systems in use, and multiple interdependencies. In addition, there are significant differences between stakeholders: airlines are completely market driven, ANSPs are national monopolies and airports are somewhere in between.

To overcome the complexity of the system, the following measures are mentioned:

- **High standardisation levels:** The telecommunication industry is mentioned as an industry where expansion has been triggered by high standardisation.
- **KPIs** at European level.
- **Avoiding in-house developments.** There is a need to have someone from outside the organisation.

3. Gap between SESAR and Deployment

Most of the results achieved in the research phase addresses nominal use cases (i.e., 80% of the total use cases), but the remaining 20% is out of research stage and thus, out of the validation, which impacts the deployment and implementation of new systems.

Increased virtualisation and increased validation effort are seen as the main solution. One must try to prevent the maturity gap by adding steps to the process making sure that the prototype is fit. Other solutions include **high standardisation, better coordination, and governance**. As an additional mitigation measure an **independent agency** is proposed as there are too many conflicting interests between the stakeholders pushing solutions before they are ready.

4. Organisational and cultural limitations

The reluctance to change is often linked to the high workload within the organisation. ANSPs also face the issue of the **transition from the legacy systems to the new ones**, especially regarding the core and **the cost of upgrading the system**. Ensuring that there are enough resources would ease the pressure. Change of culture/business model is also seen as a potential solution.

5. Extensive regulation and bureaucracy

Too much regulation (including different national regulations due to the fragmentation of the European market) and procedures including the procurement rules which lead to a high administrative burden. The bureaucracy involved in (funded) research is also perceived as excessive.

KPI's at EU level or better governance are seen as solutions. But more important is that respondents are not sure if there are too many regulations.

6. Safety critical environment

Due to the stringent safety regulation, it takes more time to develop and validate an innovative technology. Sometimes the development does not even start as there is the risk that the technology will not be approved by the safety agency.

High standardisation levels, balance between safety and flexibility and the importance of **funding and the use of incremental steps** were appointed as mitigation measures for boosting the implementation of innovative technologies in a safety critical environment.

7. Limited human resources

There is a shortage of operational staff, as the priority is to maintain the ATCO positions, so involvement in projects is lowest in priority. There is also a shortage of technical staff leading to the same experts being involved in many projects.

Regarding the **safety critical environment**, **limited human resources** and **operational difficulties for transition**, the **use of incremental steps** was proposed to be an effective way to solve these problems. **Political commitment** should be the way to ensure human and financial resources.

A need for **culture change** and **better communications with professional associations** was proposed to avoid false assumptions and division between management and professionals with consequent negative actions such as strikes of air traffic controllers.

8. Conflict of interests between stakeholders

Conflict of interest between the ANSP and the client. Usually, the benefits are for the client, leaving little incentives for the ANSPs.

A **reward system** was seen as a good measure to de-conflict the situation and move the unavoidable individual interests towards the common interest.

9. Operational difficulties for transition

Aviation is a continuous business which cannot be stopped to replace one system by another. In addition, often different systems (legacy system and new system) must be used simultaneously as not all stakeholders invest simultaneously in all systems (e.g., ADS-B). It is difficult to build a business case when two systems must work next to each other.

This was seen as one of the most important barriers in ATM. To mitigate its effect, the **incentives for adoption of innovative technologies**, such as **monetary incentives**, are important. The use of **incremental steps** would reduce risks in operational deployment and therefore the difficulties, as asserted before.

2.2.2. Factors behind the decision process

Factors are split into two distinct phases: Research and Deployment. The factors are listed in the following table:

Table 3: List of factors

	Factors	Description
Research phase	Stakeholders Operational/Technological stakeholders' involvement	This means the involvement of the different stakeholders during the research phase
	SESAR ATM needs alignment Funding for research	This is more about the global purpose of SESAR and if the solutions proposed by SESAR are aligned with the real needs of ATM. Additionally, is it important to have (European) funding to commit to the research?
	Results Maturity level Research outcomes: positive/negative impacts on KPAs and requirements Dissemination to impacted stakeholders	We distinguish here between the results themselves (hence the results of the research phase with respect to maturity level, benefits, impact, requirements, ...) and the dissemination of the results to the stakeholders. Does dissemination also play a key role in the uptake of a technology?
Deployment phase	Stakeholders Operational/Technological stakeholders' involvement	This is the involvement of the stakeholders during the deployment phase.

Stakeholder's coordination	In addition, we would like you to assess the importance of coordination between stakeholders. E.g. If there is central coordination, is a technology more likely to be implemented?
Implementation requirements Operational: Human licensing and training Technological: technology development and implementation	This means the requirements which resulted from the research phase to implement the solution (licensing, training, development of innovative technology, integration within existing technology...)
Legal Framework Policies and regulations Funding/subsidies/charges Rewards/penalisations	We distinguish two main aspects: 1) which policies must be created/modified to support the solution and if the systems need to comply with existing policies. Eg. Platform to be equipped on board may need to comply with certain laws and regulations. 2) Incentives to adopt the technology either positively (by subsidies, discount on navigation charges, priority when equipped) or negatively (by higher charges, penalties).
Business criteria Organisation Business model Willingness to change Trade-off between revenues and costs	The impact on the own company Individual cost benefit analysis (CBA) Impact can be different depending on business model-> which models are more willing to invest in innovative technologies Culture of the company – willingness to change

Table 4 List of factors – Part II

Each factor was rated depending on the importance within the decision-making process (for the figure this rating was scaled from low to high). Additionally, they are classified depending on whether the factor acted as a lever or a barrier or both. The following Figure 1 shows the results.

Figure 1 Classification of factors by importance and lever/barrier- Part II

The most important factor was the “**SESAR alignment**” since only with proper alignment with the ATM needs and with solutions addressing the current problems the interest and adoption of the solution by the different stakeholders will be triggered. This was closely followed by the **outcomes (results) of the research project itself**, in terms of performance/operational benefits. The results are the key factor to lead to a successful implementation of the concept/technology. The more positive the

benefits (economical and performance) of the concept/technology, the keener will be all affected stakeholders to adopt it. In line with this, when the negative impacts are bigger, the organisations are less motivated by this change. The **maturity, stakeholder involvement and the implementation requirements** were next in line. Maturity measures the readiness of the technology to be deployed and hence is essential for any stakeholder to support the decision-making process. The main reason for scoring stakeholder involvement so highly is the risk that the technology is not fit for the user. Moreover, if the stakeholders are involved in the development, they will be keener to deploy it. It was also stated that, today, coordinating bodies often limit their role to monitoring. Implementation requirements need to be known clearly and must be kept in mind, but it was also acknowledged that stakeholders are likely to have to adjust them. Some disenchantment with the European ATM roadmap was shown and trustful implementation expectations and timing are needed. It is important to note that a requirement not beneficial for a stakeholder should be supported with monetary incentives to palliate the negative business case. The **other factors** remain quite within the same level of importance.

Regarding the lever/barrier classification, almost all the factors are categorised between “lever” and “both” (but closer to “lever”) without any remarkable difference. **“Implementation requirements”** is the exception and clearly identified as a barrier, although a minority believes that it could be “both” as the requirements are needed to support the implementation. **Stakeholder involvement (both phases)** was categorised as being both a lever and a barrier in practice while ideally it would be a lever. In some cases it was considered a barrier since no clear coordinator has sufficient power and accountability to steer the actions of all stakeholders. **The legal** framework was seen by some as a barrier as legal requirements can be time consuming and can block the implementation. For some it could also act as a lever, since it can counteract the effects of a negative business case. **The maturity** at the end of the R&D phase is perceived as not good enough to be quickly implemented by the operational team. However, people also think that if the technology is very desirable, the level of maturity plays a smaller role as it can be solved eventually. **SESAR alignment and the outcomes (both in research and deployment phase)** are set closest to being a lever. If ATM needs are aligned with the SESAR master plan, it incentivises the adoption of the technology in the short term. However, it somehow stops the long-term research as this should not be constrained by the current ATM needs and should be given more room to disruptive and innovative ideas. Again, the better the outcomes/benefits of a technology, the more likely it will be adopted by the operational side. This does not mean that technologies which have both positive and negative impacts are not acceptable. **“Business criteria”** could be both but is closer to a lever since if alignment is achieved it triggers the adoption but even if not aligned it should not be considered a no-go factor (the legal framework would make it mandatory if necessary).

2.2.3. Decision making

According to the feedback from the interviewees, two decision-making diagrams are distinguished. The distinction lies in the trigger that pushes the adoption of either an innovative technology or a new concept. On one hand, **EC regulates the deployment** to move SESAR concepts into operations by a regulation (e.g., Common Projects). On the other hand, a specific stakeholder identifies an **own need** what leads to the implementation of the corresponding solution.

Because of the relevant differences between both processes, two flow diagrams are outlined using the same colour code: (a) blue boxes illustrate the type of company/stakeholder (e.g., airspace user); (b) green arrows and boxes represent the relationships among the different stakeholders to move forward with the deployment process; (c) orange arrows and boxes depict the main risks and issues that the different organisations may face during the deployment phase.

Figure 2: Decision making diagrams

In the first case, the process is triggered by the European Commission (EC) after conducting a large consultation with the different stakeholders. The EC produces a mandate that affects different stakeholders, depending on the solution to be deployed. The adoption of the Common projects (i.e., EC mandates) follows four steps: (i) setting the content, (ii) stakeholder consultation, (iii) endorsement and institutional consultation, and (iv) adoption. Therefore, prior to the release of the mandate, the EC first makes its own business case to decide if it is worth to deliver that mandate. Secondly, it conducts a large consultation to ensure that the different stakeholders can comply with the content and the assigned deadlines.

After the regulation approval, most stakeholders conduct an individual cost benefit analysis to particularise the net benefits from the research phase. The elaboration of an own business case lets companies prioritise the tasks (i.e., fit the solution in the tight planning) and design the process for achieving the deployment.

In the second case, the process for deciding and developing a solution that addresses a local need follows six steps (i) minor coordination + Initial planning + Initial risk assessment: this step consists basically of gathering the internal information (i.e., related exclusively to the own organisation) required to perform the business case; (ii) minor coordination for checking the available technology; (iii) develop a business case; (iv) local needs prioritisation; (v) planning; (vi) certification.

Differences between both processes are largest for the role of the National Safety Agency. In an EC mandate, NSAs counts on EASA support. During local implementations, they are not involved since the beginning and do not count on the support of EASA. This leads to both planning issues and lack of qualified personnel for the certification of the solution.

3. Quantitative assessment

In this section we take a more quantitative approach. We develop a simple model using elements of industrial economics, game theory and transport economics and apply it on two ATM technologies to illustrate the findings. This working paper only presents the main set up and findings. Hence, we will not go into the details of the analytical and numerical model. For more details we refer to (Delhaye et al., 2021).

The model focusses on the specific characteristics of ATM technologies and how these characteristics could be an obstacle to their uptake. Indeed, many ATM technologies possess some specific characteristics, namely: (i) often both the ANSP and the airlines need to make an investment, (ii) there is an imbalance in the allocation of benefits and costs as most of the investment costs are often born by the ANSP, while it is the airline that will enjoy most of the benefits and (iii) ATM technologies often display network features, in which the full benefits of upgrading a system are only realised if the whole network is upgraded leading to externalities and hence non-optimal investments.

We consider four economic agents in our model: the regulator, ANSPs, airlines and passengers. The regulator can impose policies and rules on the ANSPs and the airlines. These can be monetary incentives, such as subsidies, or certain mandates or price regulations such as caps on the navigational charges, etc. The ANSPs provide ATM services to the airlines in return for navigational charges and finally, the airlines provide air kilometres to the passengers in return of ticket fares. The model could be modified to include airports instead of airlines. However, as the analytical analysis becomes complicated very quickly when adding actors, we focus on the interaction between airlines and ANSPs.

The model is set up within a two-stage game. In a preliminary stage, the regulator sets the rules or policies. These are taken as exogenous. In the first stage, the ANSPs set the navigational charges and

decide whether to adopt the innovative technology or not. We consider several ways in which the service providers set its charges. One option is to assume the current situation where the ANSP is allowed to set its charges as to recover its costs. Another option is to impose a cap. Finally, we consider the possibility that there are no restrictions and the ANSP simply maximises its profits. In the second stage, airlines decide whether to invest in the innovative technology and choose the desired flows to maximise their profits.

We start from a simple set-up with a single ANSP and airline. In this setting, both ANSP and airline will act as monopolistic entities. We then enrich the model by allowing multiple types of airlines. This adds realism to the model as it introduces competition between airlines and allows us to gain insight in the difference in reaction of low-cost carriers (LCC) or legacy carriers (LC). In our last step we generalize the model further by considering two ANSPs, either in serial or in parallel connections on the same origin and destination. This is inspired by how transport network capacity decisions are reached. With a parallel network, in the second stage, the airlines not only set their flows but also choose their routes. Finally, we apply our model to two ATM technologies (Controller Pilot Data Link Communication (CPDLC) and Remote Towers) which exhibit distinct characteristics to illustrate how these affect the ease or difficulty to implement them.

3.1. Airlines, ANSPs and ATM technologies

We assume an airline (or multiple homogenous airlines) which serves a single market between a single origin-destination pair. For analytical purposes we assume linear demand and cost functions. The airlines profit function is simply its revenues minus its total costs where the total costs for the airlines consist of three categories; a variable cost, a fixed cost and a cost associated with congestion or delays. Variable costs are the sum of the direct operational costs such as fuel, labour and maintenance and the navigational fee which the airline pays to the ANSP for the ATM services. Navigational fees make up to 10% of the variable costs (Dempsey-Brench & N. Volta, 2018). The fixed costs are the non-operating costs (also called overhead costs) such as acquisition of aircraft or investment in infrastructure or technology. Fixed costs are typically high in the airline industry and can make up more than 50% of the total costs (Vasigh et al. 2013). Finally, the delay or congestion costs increases the costs per flight proportional to the number of flights (or passengers) and depends on the available capacity. We assume a linear marginal congestion cost such that the total congestion costs are a quadratic function of the demand. This set-up was also used in (Adler et al. 2015). The airlines revenue is determined by the demand times the average fare per km.

ANSPs are assumed to act as a monopoly. Indeed, their fixed costs, the national sovereignty, and the fact that there can only be one ANSP controlling a flight corridor makes them natural monopolies. Like the airline we assume a linear cost function for the ANSP being the sum of variable costs, such as labour and maintenance, and a fixed cost that consists of the investment costs and other sunk costs. We assume here that the ANSP does not face costs of congestion on the airspace directly. However indirectly it leads to lower provision of airflight kilometres and will impact its profits. Hence it is in its interest to reduce congestion. The ANSP has only one revenue resource which is the navigational charges collected from the airlines. The navigational charge depends on the number of kilometres flown and the weight of the aircraft (Raffarin, 2004) which is directly correlated with the size of the aircraft. Under the current regulations, ANSPs can recuperate part of its investment costs through higher charges, and these will thus depend on the investment decision of the ANSP. The profits of the ANSP are simply the revenues from the charges minus its operational costs and its fixed costs.

ATM technologies impact airlines and ANSPs cost functions in multiple ways. We examine the situation where an innovative technology is available and the ANSPs and airlines need to decide whether they want to invest in this technology or not. Their decision depends on the impacts on their profits. For

the airlines there are multiple impacts: ATM technologies reduces fuel and delay costs whilst requires investing in new equipment and retrofitting aircrafts. Technologies can also affect the costs of the ANSP: by increasing the efficiency of the air traffic controllers, operational costs can be reduced. On the other hand, fixed costs are increased due to the cost of investing.

As a first application we take the Controller Pilot Data Link Communication (CPDLC). The CPDLC is a means of communication between aircraft and ground control using data link for ATC communication. It has the possibility to drastically increase efficiency of air traffic control, by standardizing operational control messages. CPDLP can offer a solution by increasing the effective capacity of the communication channel, the number of flights one controller can handle, and the cost efficiency of the ANSP. The main implications for the airlines are that they will suffer less delay costs and rerouting will be minimized which decreases the fuel consumption. The CPDLP technology thus exhibits all the characteristics of ATM technologies mentioned above. The second technology considered, Remote Towers, only exhibits a subset of the possible characteristics. With the latest concept of remote towers, instead of having ATCOs at each airport, they will be in a centralised remote tower centre. There they can control many airports and flight routes from a distance. This technology does not require investments on the side of the airlines but large investments from the ANSPs. The main benefits are cost savings for the ANSPs. A more efficient provision of ATM services could increase its capacity, albeit smaller than for CPDLC and as such have an indirect benefit to the airlines.

3.2. Main Findings

The first insight from our analysis is that **regulation of navigation fees is necessary**, as without regulation the natural monopoly of ATM management would allow prohibitively large charges on airlines. On the other hand, too tight an enforcement of the fee may hinder any real investment in technology as the ANSP may not recover its investment cost. Regulation should therefore be tight, but not too tight to allow the ANSP to recover costs and make a small profit to allow for investment. This is very apparent in the one airline - one ANSP setting but remains true for the other settings. Whether the airline will be willing to adopt the innovative technology will depend on whether the benefits outweigh the costs.

The second insight is that the market uptake of **innovative technologies that are strong network based and have a significant impact on congestion or delay costs will be more probable in a one-to-one setting**. A (close-to) monopolistic airline internalises the benefits of lower delay costs in the airspace and will reap more the potential benefits of a reduction of the latter. The ANSP is, therefore more certain about the uptake of the airline in this setting and that it can enjoy the benefits of its investment. This may explain why the uptake of some technologies in the Canadian airspace (which has a single ANSP and a more limited number of competing airlines) was more successful than in the EU or the US. In a more competitive environment, the uptake of technologies that enhance the capacity of the airspace will be more difficult to implement. Moreover, as soon as some airlines are equipped, the remaining airlines can free ride, reducing their incentive to adopt the technology even more. On the other hand, **if the operational benefit or competitive benefit of the technology is large enough and outweighs possible network improvements, the uptake of the technology will be stimulated in a competitive environment compared to the monopolistic one**. This has implications when considering Low-cost carriers (LCC) and Legacy carriers (LC). A legacy has less flexibility to reroute and has a large market share, implying that it behaves more like a monopoly and will therefore internalize more of the network delay cost compared to a low-cost airline. This means that it responds more to technologies that have an impact on congestion. In addition, the **legacy carrier** cares more for service cost than navigation fees set by the ANSP. This means that it will **be more responsive to 'best-equipped, best-served' policies** by the ANSP. Since, the low-cost airlines do not generally own

their fleet and invest less in staff training it could mean that retrofitting additional technology may be less obvious. On the other hand, **low-cost airlines will be more responsive if the technology leads to an obvious competitive advantage and reduced variable (also fuel) cost.** In our numerical illustration, we find that for the CPDLP technology, the introduction of competition does not alter the incentives for the airlines very much. This is because CDPLD both reduces operational and delay costs and as such there is a balance between the different effects. In both settings it would be beneficial for the airlines to adopt the technology as soon as the ANSP has. However, as profit margins are much lower in the duopolistic setting, there is a tighter budget constraint and investment costs cannot run too high.

It is not clear if increased competition between ANSPs stimulates the uptake of innovative technologies or not for the ANSPs. For ANSPs that have a substantial proportion of transit traffic (as opposed to domestic air traffic that cannot divert its flight routes to avoid the ANSPs airspace), if a competing ANSP adopts an innovative technology **that has strong operational benefits to the airlines** (as is the case for CPDLP), and many airlines choose to adopt the innovative technology this traffic is diverted implying considerable losses to the ANSP. In this case there is a **strong first mover advantage and the uptake of these technologies could be facilitated in a more competitive environment.** For **technologies with little or no benefits to the airlines** (e.g., Remote Towers), the opposite can occur there **can be some free riding on the side of non-investing ANSPs.** As airlines cannot benefit from the technology, they will avoid the airspace of ANSPs that uses the innovative technologies due to increase charges to recover the investment costs. A competing ANSP that holds on to the old technology will be able to benefit from the increased demand in its airspace. Although on the long run, the ANSP with the newer technology will be able to decrease charges thanks to the decreased operating costs, a short sighted ANSP might want to delay investments.

From the airline perspective, the picture is less clear as it very much depends on the initial capacities of the ANSP before the adoption of any innovative technology. If both ANSPs are operating close to capacity, for the airlines to enjoy the full benefits of their investment both ANSPs need to use the technology. Indeed, if only one ANSP has adopted the technology the airline will increase the number of flights using this airspace but only until the benefit of using this corridor (lower operational cost, increased capacity) is compensated by the higher cost (increased navigation fee, increased congestion by increase in demand). It will, therefore, in some cases still use the corridor which uses the old technology and as such the **benefits will only apply to a share of its total flights.** In some cases, this could mean that the benefits will not be enough to compensate the costs. The fact that the airline needs both ANSPs to use the innovative technology, **increases the uncertainty and reduces its expected potential benefits of the technology** making it less prone to make the investment. If the ANSPs do not believe that the airlines will carry out the investments needed they will play safe and prefer the status quo. This will be even more the case if there is a reluctance to change.

In a serial network one ANSP may free ride on the investment of another ANSP. This does not mean that pro-competitive policies on the side of ATM and airlines do not have other welfare benefits, but we find that in a more fractured market the investment incentives are reduced.

The fourth insight is that an overall **technological mandate for a 'proven' technology can be a welfare improving solution.** This reduces the uncertainty that would be caused by a market-led uptake of the technology in a fractured and competitive market. We have, however, seen in the qualitative analysis of section 2, that there is little appetite from the stakeholder point of view for such a measure.

4. Policy options

Next, the results of the case studies, interviews and workshop, and the economic modelling were used to come to a selection of policy measures which would be of interest to invest further within the ITACA project. The selection was made from a long list of policy measures using multicriteria analysis. Criteria such as technical feasibility, economic feasibility, regulatory feasibility, acceptability by stakeholders and the feasibility to assess the policy measures using Agent Based Modelling techniques were included. To obtain robust results, different weighing factors were used. This resulted in this concise list of policy measures shown in Table 4. **This set of promising policy and regulatory measures will be explored and assessed in more detail in subsequent stages of the ITACA project and is an important first step towards a faster uptake of ATM technologies.**

Table 4: Selected policy measures

Source	Policy measure	Related issue
Case studies ATM Case studies other industries Economic modelling	<i>Direct subsidies for ANSPs (by preference conditional on implementation)</i>	Overcome the discord between high costs and goal to lower ANSP charges Overcome strict budget constraints Overcome principle agent problem (main investor is not main beneficiary)
Case studies ATM Economic modelling	<i>Best equipped-Best Served/lower charged</i>	Overcome last-mover advantage for technologies with network effects and/or decreasing costs with scale
Case studies ATM Economic modelling	<i>Flexible charging</i>	Overcome last-mover advantage for technologies with network effects and/or decreasing costs with scale
Case studies ATM Stakeholder consultation	<i>Demonstration projects, Increased validation efforts, visualisation, dissemination</i>	Overcome inherent reluctance to change, opposition social partners, safety concerns Showing the benefits and hence decreasing uncertainty
Case studies ATM	<i>Realistic timelines, with this we mean that the timeframe to implement certain technologies should be set realistically instead of postponing deadlines as (unrealistic or overoptimistic) targets are not reached.</i>	Overcome inherent reluctance to change, opposition social partners

Stakeholder consultation	<i>Increase matureness technologies⁴</i>	Overcome gap between TRL4 and deployment Overcome reluctance to change Overcome human resource shortage at ANSPs
Stakeholder consultation	<i>Involvement of the safety agent in the research phase</i>	Overcome safety concerns
Case studies ATM Economic modelling	<i>Mandates (with strict and credible enforcement)</i>	Overcome current charging regulation which creates low incentives Overcome reluctance to change, opposition social partners

5. Conclusions

This paper analyses the main levers and barriers for the adoption of innovative technologies by the different ATM stakeholders. For this purpose, a mix of qualitative and quantitative methods are employed. The qualitative assessment is based on a review of literature and case studies, interviews with key players in the industry and a workshop. The case studies focus on successful and unsuccessful experiences related to the uptake of innovative technologies. The primary focus of the case studies is on innovation in the aviation sector but also includes the experience in other industries, especially in network industries such as rail, electricity, and telecom. This combination of desk research and stakeholder consultation is used to identify the potential explanatory factors behind the experiences, helping us understand the reasons and conditions for the success or failure of the implementation of innovative technologies. This initial qualitative assessment also serves to depict several mechanisms linked to the adoption of innovative technologies. These are then investigated by means of quantitative economic modelling. The **first insight** from the quantitative analysis is that **regulation of navigation fees is necessary**, as without regulation the natural monopoly of ATM would allow prohibitively large charges on airlines. However, too tight an enforcement of the fee may stymie any real investment in technology as the ANSP may not recover its investment cost. **Regulation should therefore be flexible enough** to allow the ANSP to recover costs and make a small profit to allow for investment. The **second insight** is that the **market uptake of innovative technologies in a one-to-one setting is easier**. The **third and connected insight**, is that it is **not clear if increased competition between ANSPs will stimulate the uptake of innovative technologies**. Innovative technology with **strong operational benefits to the airlines** (as is the case for CPDLP), **could be facilitated in a more competitive environment but for technologies with little or no benefits to the airlines** (e.g., Remote Towers), the opposite can occur there **can be some free riding on the side of non-investing ANSPs**. Moreover, the incentives for the airlines to invest are reduced as **benefits will only apply to a share of its total flights, increasing the uncertainty on the expected benefits for the ANSPs**. In a serial network one ANSP may free-ride on the investment of

⁴ Increasing maturity level technology” was added to the result of the MCA as this was deemed very important by the stakeholders and its lower score was mainly related to the feasibility of ABM as it is rather a policy goal than a policy instrument.

another ANSP, while the overall benefit for airlines is reduced. This does not mean that pro-competitive policies on the side of ATM and airlines do not have other welfare benefits, but we find that in a more fractured market the investment incentives are reduced. The **fourth insight**- which is also supported by numerical analysis - is that an **overall technological mandate for a 'proven' technology can be a welfare improving solution**. This reduces the uncertainty that would be caused by a market-led uptake of the technology in a fractured and competitive market.

The conclusions of both the initial qualitative assessment and the economic modelling are then used within a multicriteria analysis to define a set of promising policy and regulatory measures. These are explored in more detail in subsequent stages of the project.

6. References

1. ACCHANGE, <https://www.tmluven.be/en/project/acchange>
2. Adler N., Hanany E., Proost S., (2015), Managing change in European air traffic control provision, Proceedings of the 11th USA/Europe Air Traffic Management Research and Development Seminar, ATM 2015
3. Arrow, K.J. (1962), Economic Welfare and the Allocation of Resources for Invention, Chapter in NBER (1962), The Rate and Direction of Inventive Activity: Economic and Social Factors <http://www.nber.org/books/univ62-1>
4. Belleflamme, P. & M. Peitz, (2012), Industrial Organization: Markets and Strategies, Cambridge University Press.
5. Berkeley, N. et al (2017), Assessing the transition towards Battery Electric Vehicles: A Multi-Level Perspective on drivers of, and barriers to, take up.
6. Berkhout, A.J & P.A. van der Duijn (2007), New ways of innovation; an application of the cyclic innovation model to the mobile phone industry, International Journal of Technology Management, Vol 40 (4)
7. COMPAIR , <https://www.compair-project.eu/>
8. Delhaye, E., S. Van der Loo, C. Heyndricks, D. Zheng Zhang and A. Fabio, "Identification of levers and barriers for the adoption of new ATM technologies", deliverable D2.1, ITACA (<https://www.itaca-h2020.eu/>), available soon
9. Dempsey-Brench, Z. & N.Volta (2018), A Cost-Efficiency Analysis of European Air Navigation Service Providers, Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice, Vol. 111, 11-23
10. European Alternative Fuels Observatory (2021), On the electrification path: Europe's progress towards clean transportation
11. European Court of Auditors (2019), Special Report: The EU's regulation for the modernisation of air traffic management has added value- but the funding was largely unnecessary,
12. Glass V. et al (2018), Unbundling reliability: lessons from the telecom industry, The Electricity Journal 31, 1-7
13. Greene, D.L., Park, S., Liu, C. (2014) Analyzing the transition to electric drive vehicles in the US, Futures 58, 34-52
14. https://www.skybrary.aero/index.php/Remote_Tower_Service
15. Papazoglou, M.E, Spanos, Y.E (2018) Bridging distant technological domains: A longitudinal study of the determinants of breadth of innovation diffusion, Research Policy 47, 1713-1728
16. Raffarin M., Congestion in European Airspace: a pricing solution? Journal of Transport Economics and Policy, University of Bath, 2004, 38 (1), pp 109-125. Hal-01021572

17. Rogers E.M. (2010), Diffusion of innovation, fourth edition, Simon & Schuster
18. Rogers E.M. (1962), Diffusion of innovation, first edition, New York: Free Press of Glencoe
OCLC 254636
19. Roupas, P. (2008), Human and Organisational Factors Affecting Technology uptake by Industry, *Innovation* 10(1), 4-28, DOI: 10.5172/impp.453.10.1.4.
20. Schumpeter, J.A. (1943) *Capitalism, Socialism and Democracy*, London: Unwin.
21. Vasigh, B., Fleming, K., Tacker, T. (2013), *Introduction to Air Transport Economics: from theory to application. Second Edition*, Routledge